

FORMATION OF THE LABOR POTENTIAL OF RURAL TERRITORIES AND WAYS OF ITS EFFECTIVE USE

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Abstract: In this article, the study of labor potential reveals its content and essence in a resource style, both qualitative and quantitative. The formation of the labor potential of the village as a socio-economic category, its research and study have gone through several stages. As a result of the development of socio-economic relations, the meaning and content of such economic concepts and categories as "labor force", "labor resources", "labor potential" also changes somewhat. These concepts have become widely used not only in the scientific and economic literature, but also in our daily practice. In the economic literature, there are still different views on the concept of the labor potential of society, and these concepts remain the subject of controversy due to the need to differentiate from it the concepts of "labor resources" and "labor force" related to this concept.

Keywords: labor potential, labor force, quality, quantity, labor resources, category, labor resources, demographic processes

Annotatsiya : Ushbu maqolada qishloq mehnat salohiyatini tadqiq etish uning resurs tarzidagi mazmuni va mohiyatini ham sifat, ham miqdor jihatidan ochib beradi. Qishloq mehnat salohiyatining ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy kategoriya sifatida shakllanishi, uning tadqiq etilishi va o'rganilishi bir necha bosqichlarni bosib o'tdi. Ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy munosabatlarning rivojlanib borishi natijasida «ishchi kuchi», «mehnat resurslari», «mehnat salohiyati» kabi iqtisodiy tushuncha va kategoriyalarning ham ma'no va mazmuni birmuncha o'zgarib bormoqda. Bu tushunchalar faqat ilmiy-iqtisodiy adabiyotlarda emas, balki kundalik amaliyotimizda ham keng foydalanila boshlandi. Iqtisodiy adabiyotlarda hozirgacha jamiyatning mehnat salohiyati tushunchasiga turli xil qarashlar mavjud bo'lib, bu tushuncha bilan bog'liq bo'lgan «mehnat resurslari» va «ishchi kuchi» tushunchalarini undan farqlash zaruriyati bo'lganligi sababli ushbu tushunchalar munozarali masala bo'lib qolmoqda.

Kalit so'zlar: mehnat salohiyati, ishchi kuchi, sifat, miqdor, mehnat resurslari, kategoriya, mehnat resurslari, demografik jarayonlar,

Аннотация: В данной статье исследование трудового потенциала раскрывает его содержание и сущность в ресурсном стиле, как качественном, так и количественном. Становление трудового потенциала сельского как социально-экономической категории, его исследование и изучение прошли несколько этапов. В результате развития социально-экономических отношений значение и содержание таких экономических понятий и категорий, как «рабочая сила», «трудовые ресурсы», «трудовой потенциал» также несколько меняется. Эти понятия стали широко использоваться не только в научно-экономической литературе, но и в нашей повседневной практике. В экономической литературе до сих пор существуют различные взгляды на понятие трудового потенциала общества, и эти понятия остаются предметом споров в связи с

необходимостью дифференциации от него связанных с этим понятием понятий «трудовые ресурсы» и «рабочая сила».

Ключевые слова: трудовой потенциал, рабочая сила, качество, количество, трудовые ресурсы, категория, трудовые ресурсы, демографические процессы,

In the following years, certain work will be carried out to reform the country's agriculture, in particular to improve the system of public administration in the industry, the widespread introduction of market relations, strengthening the legal basis of relations between entities producing, processing and selling agricultural products, attracting investment in the industry, the introduction of resource-saving technologies and providing agricultural producers with modern equipment.

.1 O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Sh. MIRZIYOYEV 2019-yil 23-oktabr, PF-5853-son

In order to diversify production, improve land and water relations, create a favorable agribusiness environment and a high value chain, support the development of cooperative relations, widespread introduction of market mechanisms, information and communication technologies into the industry, as well as effective use of scientific achievements and increase human resources: with the participation of international organizations and experts, a Strategy for the development of agriculture has been published the economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2030 (hereinafter referred to as the strategy) Roadmap "on the implementation of the tasks set by the Strategy for the Development of Agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2030.

Development and implementation of the state food safety policy, which provides for ensuring food security and improving the diet of consumption, the production of food in the required quantities;

Widespread introduction of market principles in the procurement and marketing of agricultural products, development of quality control infrastructure, export promotion, creation of a favorable agribusiness environment and value chain, involving the production of competitive agricultural and food products with high added value in target international markets;

Introduction of mechanisms to reduce state participation and increase the investment attractiveness of the industry, providing for an increase in the inflow of private investment capital to support modernization, diversification and sustainable growth of agriculture and food;

Rational use of natural resources, which provides for the rational use of land and water resources, the forest fund and the improvement of the environmental protection system; Development of modern management systems providing for restructuring and further development of the structure of public administration in agriculture; increasing efficiency and gradual redistribution of public spending through the development of sectoral programs aimed at increasing labor productivity on farms, improving product quality, creating high added value; development of a system of scientific, educational, information and consulting services in agriculture, providing for the use of effective forms of dissemination of knowledge and information integrated with the production of research, educational and consulting services;

Reforms on the formation and effective use of labor resources. In our country, labor resources make up about 60% of the population. Labor resources have the physical and mental abilities

to create material goods and services in the process of work. The inactive population included in the labor force, not participating in social production, makes up the labor reserve. Because over time they can also join the economically active population. According to the State Statistics Committee, the number of population and labor resources in the Republic of Uzbekistan is regularly increasing. Uzbekistan is conditionally divided into 3 territorial units according to the state of labor resources: Ferghana Valley, Samarkand region, Khorezm region. There are excessive labor resources, few jobs. Mirzachul, Navoi district of Bukhara. There is little labor force here, and the factor of natural resources is sufficient for the development of production. Tashkent region. There is a lot of both labor and jobs here. It is no secret that it would not be an exaggeration to say that due to the specifics of our country, primarily demographic, employment issues remain relevant and acute. Demographic processes and the formation of labor resources the quantity and quality of labor resources occupy an important place in the economies of countries. In 2022, labor resources in Uzbekistan accounted for 59.5% of the total population. In the period after 2022, the number of labor resources increases by about 400 thousand people per year on average. In previous years, the average life expectancy of Uzbeks has increased from 67 to 73 years. Women's life expectancy of our mothers exceeds 75 years, this factor, determined by the level of social and economic development of the state, in turn, plays a decisive role in its development and progress. The population of the republic in 2022 will be 34.4 million people. Currently, the country's population growth is about 1.8% on average per year. The age composition of the population of Uzbekistan is approximately:

1. 0-15 years 30.3 %;
2. Men 16-60 years old, women 16-55 years 59.5 %;
3. Men aged 60 years and older and women aged 55 years and older make up 10.2 %.

In Uzbekistan, about 30.3% of the population is under 15 years of age. The natural population growth in 2022 was 18.6 people per 1000 population. At the beginning of 2020, 16.8 million people lived in rural areas. 49.4% of the population lived in rural areas. The total rural population is about 8.8 million people. 54.08% of the population, is of working age. Of these, 5.5 million people (70.5%) are employed. Statistics show that approximately 30.9% of the employed population is employed in agriculture. These data on the population determine how important it is for the agriculture of the Republic. The main problem with employment bases in rural areas is that the number of jobs is below the level of demand. It arose due to the fact that not all branches of agriculture were sufficiently developed for long periods of time. Such discrepancies may be caused by unemployment, the desire to work, but for different reasons.

The formation of the labor market and its regulation is one of the most important and urgent issues in the conditions of market relations. The labor market is an important link between various industries and sectors of the economy. The labor market is an attitude to the purchase and sale of labor, and the law of supply and demand operates on it. This is where the purchase and sale of labor takes place in a competitive environment. On one side of the labor market is the owner of the labor force, and on the other - an enterprise, a firm in need of labor. There is an exchange connection between them. Thus, the demand for labor and the supply of labor are related to each other. The labor market is inextricably linked with other market systems, and in order to be really in demand, the labor force must have a certain set of physical, mental and professional abilities.

2 Чижов Н.А. Управление корпоративными кадрами. – М.: Питер Принт, 2005, 31-с. 2
Колосова Р.П. Экономика труда. – М.: МГУ, 2004, 42-с.

Applying these abilities to the production process, it must be constantly reproduced in order not to lose its consumer qualities. 3 The aggregate demand for labor is regulated by the volume of investment and production. Some researchers believe that the labor market creates conditions for meeting supply and demand through a direct agreement between employers and those who want to hire employees, as well as ensures the purchase of labor. Of great scientific and practical importance for our republic is the study of the concept, composition, characteristics and tasks of the labor market, which is one of the most effective tools for solving the problem of increasing the employment of the able-bodied population. In the republic, more than 60% of the able-bodied population lives in rural areas and produces more than 40% of GDP; – the share of rural labor resources not employed in agriculture due to lack of jobs is a significant proportion of the total unemployed population of the republic, and their number is growing ;p the share of the working-age population not employed in agriculture due to a shortage of jobs, is the qualification of people is an obstacle to the movement of people to areas with a low level of employment towards the facilities of foreign countries; When studying the issues of formation and development of the labor market, of course, an analysis of its components is necessary. The main elements of the labor market component include: the demand for labor and its supply, cost, price and competition in hiring. Demand reflects the volume and structure of demand, an orderly social infrastructure of production and the labor market of other sectors of the national economy, provided with a wage fund, income from personal subsidiary farms and other vital tools. The offer is a quantitative and qualitative (in terms of quantity, gender, age, education, profession, qualifications, etc.) structure of the workforce interested in getting a job, subject to hiring. It should be noted that a systematic study of the socio-economic content of the concept of "labor market" and its components makes it possible to identify the main tasks that this market performs:

3. Chepurenko A.Yu. Predprinimatelstvo kak sfera sotsialnyh issledovaniy: opyt//<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/282847838>

Predprinimatelstvo_kak_sfera_socialnyh_issledovaniy_rossia_i_mezdunarodnyj_opyt.

Freedom and voluntary work is the main condition or condition for the formation of the labor market. Along with this, there are a number of economic, social, demographic, climatic and legal conditions and factors that directly affect the formation of the labor market. The main economic condition for the formation of the labor market is the individual ownership of employees in relation to their labor force and the collective or private ownership of employers in workplaces. It should be borne in mind here that the entry of these subjects into exchange relations is due to their personal interests, which are backed by personal consumerism. They, in turn, will be an expression of only the necessary social needs of the socio-economic life of the population in reproduction. The emergence of the labor market requires that there be free and equal partners in economic relations, ready to compete with each other to achieve a balance between the supply and demand of labor. In the market, the

mercenary and the employer are interconnected in terms of personal freedom and economic necessity, and also oppose each other, even if they depend on each other. Achieving a market equilibrium between the supply and demand of labor is one of the defining economic conditions for the formation of the labor market. But there is no such balance. The main reason for this is the rapid growth in the number of the working-age population offered in comparison with the volume of demand for it. Structural changes in all sectors of the economy in modern conditions are one of the 17 most important economic conditions that determine the new movement of demand and supply for labor in the labor market. In the scientific works of Western experts on labor law, an employment contract is expressed as "an agreement on the obligation of an employee to work for remuneration and the presence of legal subordination. A contract is a kind of private-law type of procurement, in respect of which the norms, possibilities and necessity of applying the norms characteristic of civil law are justified. The main feature of the employment contract is that its conclusion necessarily entails subordination and dependence, in addition, expresses the nature of reliability and long-term legal relations arising. Subordination of an employee to an employer in an economic sense is considered as the main feature of an employment contract. This subordination, as a rule, is not only socio-economic, technical, organizational, but also legal and social protection by employers of employees of Uzbekistan; Free establishment of the salary limit and other legitimate incomes in compliance with the established Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan "not lower than the required subsistence minimum." At the same time, the study of factors directly affecting the growth of demand acquires the greatest socio-economic importance. Factors justifying the growth in demand for labor include: creation of new jobs in disadvantaged industries, attracting foreign investment, expansion of the manufacturing industry, provision of services and self-employment, development of small businesses and private entrepreneurship, etc. At the same time, factors that reduce the supply of labor and the need for jobs arise and begin to influence: personal subsidiary farming, individual labor activity, private entrepreneurship and self- However, there are also such factors that together have a significant impact on the state of formation of the labor supply. These include: natural and mechanical movements of those who want to work, employees and employers; a fund of funds necessary for life; monetary incomes of employees; The financial capabilities of the family; the number of people engaged in "domestic work" without hiring; the number of employees in the Armed Forces and the length of service in them; improvement of alternative and qualified professional services, etc. The increase or decrease (dynamics) of labor demand is determined by changes in the following quantitative and qualitative indicators: existing and new There are also a number of restrictions that hinder the effective formation of the labor market in Uzbekistan; the rise in price of consumer goods; low qualifications and mobilization of hired labor; insufficient experience of employers, etc. Thus, the implementation of the concept of political development of the "Uzbek model" is carried out on the basis of such principles as an ideology-free economy, gradual introduction of democratic reforms, ensuring the rule of law, recognition of the role of the state as the main reformer and its influence during the transition period, carrying out a strong social policy taking into account the specifics of our country.

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